

A STUDY OF LOCUS OF CONTROL TOWARDS DEGREE LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The study aimed to assessment the locus of control of students at degree level Participants were 300 degree students studying in under graduate and post graduate (174 males, 126 females) degree level students from some districts in Tamilnadu. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between degree level students. The tool used for the present study is Locus of Control Scale Constructed and Standardized by Dr. Jayasree P & Jayasree P.G. (2006). Results of this study concluded that there exists average level of locus of control of degree students such as gender, locality of college, type of management, students residence and degree obtained further it shows there is no significant difference between degree students towards gender, locality of college, type of management, students residence and degree obtained towards locus of control.

Introduction:

The field of Education has drawn from various disciplines and incorporated facts and principles of psychology. Walter B. Kolesnik defines Educational Psychology as A study of those facts and principles of psychology that help to explain and improve the process of education. The process of development in education would revolve around characteristics and quality of teacher, student, student-teacher interaction and situations in which it occurs. The importance of education and its effect on individual is widely known and therefore extensive research and attempts are ongoing in this field to broaden existing knowledge and research.

Locus of Control:

Locus of control is a generalized expectancy about the degree to which individuals control their outcomes (Rotter, 1966). Kelly (1969) says that, Locus of control refers to how far individuals see themselves as in control of and responsible for the course of occurrences (desirable and undesirable) which they experience. The concept of locus of control derived from Rotter's social learning theory (Roddenberry & Renk, 2008). Rotter argued that locus of control stemmed from ones generalized expectancy about the world. A person whose efforts are consistently rewarded develops an internal locus of control, whereas people who do not succeed despite their efforts acquire an external locus of control (Twenge, Zhang & Im, 2004). Internals therefore see a causal relationship between their behavior and rewards, whereas externals tend not to make this connection (Rotter, 1990).

Locus of control is a concept that has a significant effect on our daily lives. Those with an external locus of control believe that their own actions do not influence future outcomes. This makes individuals less likely to work to reach their full potential due to the motivational, emotional, and cognitive deficits it creates. In fact, people with an external locus of control are more likely to suffer from depression and other ailments because they believe their actions cannot improve their current position. Attribution theory provides a basis on which individuals judge the stable versus fluctuating qualities of other people (such as motives, intentions or characteristics). Attribution theory is concerned with causal inferences and based on this conceptualization of locus of control the question posed is "To what can X- outcome (e.g. success or wellbeing) be attributed?" (Taylor, Schepers & Crous; 2006).

Methodology: Normative survey method was followed.

Sample: In the present study, the students of degree studying at under graduate and post graduate students of some districts in Tamilnadu were taken as the sample and the size of the sample is 300.

Statement of the Problem: The problem chosen for the study may be stated as "A Study of Locus of Control towards Degree Level Students".

Objectives of the study:

To study the levels of locus of control of students degree level belonging to the following sub-samples are

- | | |
|-----------------------|--------------------------------|
| ✓ Gender | : Male/ Female |
| ✓ Locality of College | : Rural / Urban |
| ✓ Type of Management | : Government / Private / Aided |
| ✓ Student Residence | : Rural / Urban |
| ✓ Degree Obtained | : UG / PG |

To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of locus of control between male and female.

To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of locus of control between rural and urban.

To find out whether the significant difference exists among sub samples of type of management with respect to their locus of control of students at degree level.

To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of locus of control between rural and urban of students at degree level of students residence.

To find out whether the significant difference exists in the mean scores of locus of control between degree obtained of students at degree level.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The levels of locus of control of students degree level belonging to the following sub-samples is high

- ✓ Gender : Male/ Female
- ✓ Locality of College : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Type of Management : Government / Private / Aided
- ✓ Student Residence : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Degree Obtained : UG / PG

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control between male and female.

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control between rural and urban.

There is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their locus of control of students at degree level.

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control between rural and urban of students at students residence.

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of locus of control between degree obtained of students at degree level.

Operational Definition of Key Term Used:

Locus of Control:

Locus of control refers to the extent to which an individual believes whether the events in his/her life are controlled by external or internal factors.

Statistical Techniques Used:

The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, Standard Deviation 't' test and 'F' test to accept or reject hypotheses.

Data Analysis:

The data collected from the sample population were systematically coded, tabulated and organized for analysis. The coded data were entered in to Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the data. In addition, t-test was used to see if there is statistically significant difference between students actual and desired level of participation in test anxiety.

Tool Used For the Present Study:

Locus of Control Scale Constructed and Standardized by Dr. Jayasree P & Jayasree P.G. (2006).

Description of the Tool:

Locus of Control:

One's "Locus" (Latin for "place" or "location") can either be internal (meaning the person believes that they control their life) or external (meaning they believe that their environment, some higher power, or other people control their decisions and their life).

Scoring Procedure of the Locus of Control:

The scale was developed following the Likert's method. For scoring the scale, a score of 5,4,3,2, and 1 was given to category. The sum of the scores of all the statements constituted the total score of the scale. The maximum and minimum scores, which the students may score on LOCS, will be 240 and 48 respectively. There are five response categories: A (Strongly agree), B (Agree), C (Undecided), D (Disagree) and E (Strongly disagree) for each of the seventy items.

Descriptive Analysis for Locus of Control Scores of Students at Degree Level:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Students of Degree Level towards Locus of Control

Demographic Variables	Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	174	142.87	7.57
	Female	126	144.39	9.05
Locality of college	Rural	146	143.56	8.04
	Urban	154	143.47	8.46
Mode of Management	Government	80	145.53	9.30
	Private	119	143.22	7.09

	Aided	101	142.25	8.41
Student Residence	Rural	146	143.56	8.04
	Urban	154	143.47	8.46
Degree Obtained	UG	138	142.59	7.25
	PG	162	144.30	8.96

Entire Sample:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of entire sample was 146.53 and the standard deviations value is 9.97 which indicate that students at degree level have average level towards locus of control.

Gender:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of male and female students at degree level are found to be 142.87 and 144.39 respectively. These mean scores indicate that both male and female students at degree level have average level towards locus of control.

Locality of College:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of rural and urban locality of college are found to be 143.56 and 143.47 respectively. These mean scores indicate that both rural and urban locality of college have average level towards locus of control.

Mode of Management:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of students of degree level belonging to other mode of management, Government, Private and Aided are 154.53 with 1443.22 and 142.25 respectively. All the sub samples of mode of management have average level of locus of control.

Student Residence:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of rural and urban residence of students are found to be 143.56 and 143.47 respectively. These mean scores indicate that both rural and urban residence of students have average level towards locus of control.

Degree Obtained:

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated mean score of UG and PG degree obtained of students at degree level are found to be 142.59 and 144.30 respectively. These mean scores indicate that both UG and PG degree obtained of students at degree level have average level towards locus of control.

Differential Analysis – Locus of Control:

This part deals with the differential analysis of data, among important objectives stated earlier was to study is there any significant difference between selected sub- samples of the present investigation on locus of control. For the purpose, the investigator decided to apply the test of significance ('t' test and 'F' test). The investigator also framed the null hypothesis for testing. The calculated values are given in the following tables.

Gender and Locus of Control:

Table 2: 't' test between Mean Scores of Male and Female Students at degree level towards Locus of Control

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	174	142.87	7.57	1.576	Not Significant
Female	126	144.39	9.05		

It is evident from the Table 2, the calculated 't' value is 1.576, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female students of degree level with respect to their locus of control.

Locality of College and Locus of Control:

Table 3: 't' test between Mean Scores of Rural and Urban locality of college towards Locus of Control

Locality of college	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	146	143.56	8.04	0.092	Not Significant
Urban	154	143.47	8.46		

It is evident from the Table 3, the calculated 't' value is 0.092, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban locality of college students towards locus of control.

Type of Management and Locus of Control:

Table 4: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Type of Management with Respect To Their Locus of Control

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	496.848	248.424	2	3.716	NS
Within Groups	19856.068	66.855	297		
Total	20352.917		299		

It is evident from the Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 3.716, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their locus of control of students at degree level.

Student residence and Locus of Control:

Table 5: 't' test between Mean Scores of Rural and Urban residence of college towards Locus of Control

Residence of student	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	146	143.56	8.04	0.126	Not Significant
Urban	154	143.47	8.46		

It is evident from the Table 5, the calculated 't' value is 0.126, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban residence of students towards locus of control.

Degree Obtained:

Table 6: 't' test between Mean Scores of UG and PG degree obtained towards Locus of Control

Degree obtained	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
UG	138	142.59	7.25	1.794	Not Significant
PG	162	144.30	8.96		

It is evident from the Table 6, the calculated 't' value is 1.794, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between UG and PG degree obtained towards locus of control.

Major Findings of the Study:

The present study basically designed to examine the higher secondary students in Vellore District. The major findings drawn from the present study are given below:

- ✓ It is found that the students at degree level of their entire sample, gender, locality of college, type of management, student residence, degree obtained have average level of locus of control.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female students of degree level with respect to their locus of control.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban locality of college students towards locus of control.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their locus of control of students at degree level.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban residence of students towards locus of control.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between UG and PG degree obtained towards locus of control.

Suggestions for the Further Research:

The following suggestions are given for further research

- ✓ A similar study involving the different degree level students of other Districts of Tamil nadu may be undertaken.
- ✓ A similar study involving the students belonging to the other courses may be taken up.
- ✓ A similar study involving other psychological variables may be studied.
- ✓ The present study could be undertaken at various states in India.

References:

1. Best, John, W., & Khan, James, V. (2008) Research in Education, Tenth Edition, New Delhi. Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd.
2. Garrett, Henry & Wood Worth, R.S.(2008). Statistics in Psychology and Education, Surjeet Publications Ltd, New Delhi.
3. Guilford. J.P (1956) "Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education" New York, Mc Graw-Hill Book Company, Inc.
4. Kelly, G. A. (1969). Man's Construction of His Alternatives. In Clinical Psychology and Personality the Selected Papers of George Kelly. Ed. Maher, B. New York. Wiley, 67-93.
5. Lokesh Kovi (1990), "Methodology of Educational Research" (2nd ed) New Delhi, Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.
6. Roddenberry, A. & Renk, K. (2008). Quality of Life In Pediatrics Cancer Patients: The Relationships among Parents' Characteristics, Childrens Characteristics, and Concordance among Informants. Journal of Child and Family Studies. 17 (3), 402-426.
7. Rotter, J. B. (1966). Generalized Expectancies for Internal Versus External Control of Reinforcement. Psychological Monographs. 80, Whole No. 609.

8. Taylor, C. M., Schepers, J. M., & Crous, F. (2006). Locus of Control in Relation to Flow. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 32 (3), 63-71.
9. Twenge, J.M., Zhang, L., & Im, C. (2004). Its beyond my control: A Cross Temporal Meta Analysis of Increasing Externality in Locus of Control, 1960-2002. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 8, 308-319.